

**GENDER STEREOTYPES AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF
GENDER DIFFERENCES IN FAMILIES**

Nazarova Gulnora Norbekovna

Psychologist, teacher, Department of
"Military Psychology and Pedagogy"

Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: the article reveals the concept of gender, its stereotypes, the essence of social norms of behavior, the theory of roles in families, the role of women and men in the family, various values and their content.

Keywords: gender, family, sex, difference, criterion, factors, essence, society, dominant, responsibility, importance, personality, character.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of gender has become one of the important categories of human social life. For representatives of one sex of society, a specific set of norms and rules of behavior differs from the requirements for the other sex. In society, culture instills different values and norms of social behavior in men and women and does not approve of their violation. Gender concepts vary in different forms of society, but often these systems are asymmetrical, with everything "masculine" (character traits, behaviors, professions, etc.) defined as primary, important, and dominant, and everything "feminine" as secondary, socially insignificant, and subordinate. The set of expected behaviors (or norms) for men and women, as well as the learned behaviors that determine the activities, tasks, and responsibilities that are perceived as masculine and feminine, are called gender roles. They are formed and developed in an individual under the influence of society and culture.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Gender roles are diverse, and their content changes in the course of the historical development of society. Each person plays a variety of roles, such as wife, sister,

mother, businesswoman, or father, husband, friend, honor student, etc. There is evidence that playing multiple roles contributes to a person's psychological well-being. Roles or components of roles can contradict each other, in which case they cause role conflict. Gender stereotypes should be distinguished from gender roles - generalized ideas (beliefs) formed in society about how men and women should behave. For this, there are special terms and words that describe men and women in different ways, all of which embody separately reflected forms of manifestation of the public consciousness - stereotypes. Traditionally, the word stereotype is understood as a certain scheme, on the basis of which the perception and evaluation of information is carried out. This scheme performs the function of generalizing a certain phenomenon, object. Usually with its help a person acts, evaluates events or acts automatically without thinking. The concept of a social stereotype denotes the ability of a person. To assess the world around him in a generalized way, to draw positive and critical conclusions, serves as its basis. The positive side of social stereotypes is that they teach to act quickly in the face of lack of information or ongoing changes and conditions. It is difficult for society to overcome historically formed gender stereotypes, and the acceptance of women's leadership has always been painful. The formation of democratic institutions and the development of political culture, in turn, serve to develop equality in political rights in society. In various crisis situations, stereotypes about abilities and role functions manifest themselves. Usually women become candidates for dismissal, and preference is given to men when hiring. As a result, the unemployment rate of women is higher than that of men. Society is developing in such a way that women receive less pay for the same work, and in addition, the exclusion of women from highly paid positions is significantly increasing. Communication in gender relations is also formed in the private sphere, the basis of which is the family, which dominates among other social institutions. Basically, it is here that interpersonal relationships that arise in a person's kinship environment are formed. In gender construction, it is the concepts of home and family that are the source of a woman's specific experience and at the same time the center of her suppression and oppression.

RESULTS

In gender relations, communication is also formed in the private sphere, the basis of which is the family, which dominates among other social institutions. Basically, it is here that interpersonal relationships that arise in a person's kinship environment are formed. In gender construction, it is the concepts of home and family that are the source of a woman's specific experience and at the same time the center of her suppression and oppression. Gender roles are distributed in the home and family on the basis of traditional gender socialization with patriarchal relations. The rules and rights of the "home world" and the role of men in it play a major role in building unequal opportunities for women and men. The perception and assessment of family information is manifested in everyday life and defines gender as an important category of social life. For example, in typical families, the word "woman" is associated with such concepts as housing, household, motherhood, children, upbringing. The word "man" is close to such concepts as supporting the family, financial income, the role of father and protector, and other similar ones. Therefore, L.V. Shtyleva defines gender stereotypes as "ideas about the differences between men and women that are stable for a given society in a given historical period."

Family gender stereotypes describe the qualities and characteristics of men and women, and include normative behavioral models that reflect generalized thoughts and ideas about men and women, taking into account gender. "Both women and men are assigned certain social roles. For example, in society, men are evaluated by their professional success, and women by their family and children. The content of gender stereotypes in different cultures is somewhat similar. For example, according to a study conducted among students from 25 countries, it was found that in the respective cultures, courage, independence, strength, desire for power and dominance are considered qualities of men, and tenderness, dependence, fantasy, emotionality, submissiveness and weakness are considered qualities of women. On the other hand, the same study also proved that qualities such as laziness, arrogance, boastfulness and disorder are attributed to different sexes in different cultures. Since gender stereotypes

depend on the gender roles accepted in a particular society, their content and degree of expression can vary in different cultures and change along with gender roles within a culture throughout history. For example, when the linotype was used to print newspapers at the end of the 19th century, printers began to hire women to service the linotype. (who could be paid less than men), and justified this by the fact that women were naturally incapable of operating such equipment and running a printing business. However, later, with the spread of typewriters, it was women who began to work en masse as typists, and their writing skills were beyond doubt. When computer typing replaced the linotype in the 1970s, this field was also dominated by women. The widespread perception in Western societies that women were naturally incapable of operating technology disappeared during World War II, when women massively replaced men in manufacturing. On the other hand, as some researchers have noted, the idea of women's natural unsuitability for productive work never applied to working-class women who combined work outside the home with household chores. Gender differences have long attracted the attention of scientists in various fields. For a long time, the main goal of researchers studying gender differences has been to find scientific evidence for gender stereotypes and thus provide a reliable basis for existing gender roles. However, this goal has generally not been achieved: most studies find more similarities than differences between men and women, and the small differences that are identified are often of a clearly social nature.

DISCUSSION

For example, men, unlike women — in full accordance with their gender roles — do not consider themselves to be very empathetic, but measurements of physiological and facial reactions show that there is no difference in direct empathic reactions between men and women. Other studies show that men experience anger, sadness, and fear just as often as women, but they often express anger and suppress other negative emotions, while women, on the contrary, suppress anger, express sadness, and fear. Of course, modern marriage differs in its content from the family institution of previous historical periods, in particular, significant changes have occurred in the natural,

functional subordination of husband and wife in marriage. In the process of gender self-awareness, the subjective experience of a person increases and the process of his active self-development accelerates. This process, in turn, makes it possible to highlight the socio-psychological aspect of the formation of marital relations. Based on the results of research in the field of gender socialization, it is emphasized that the features of determining the sexual role of a man and a woman in marriage are clearly reflected in the position of a person in society, his personal and professional fate. In this sense, they are of great importance in reflecting the processes taking place in our time, and the main direction of their development is the increasing need for the spiritual and moral development of the individual. Marital roles can be divided into three main types: traditional, friendly, and cooperative roles. Adaptation to the main role, of course, involves the coordination of ideas about the nature and distribution of family responsibilities. The first feature of adaptation is that the spouses choose the same type of role. The second is that the main components of the family and extra-family behavior required for this role are consistent for each of the husband and wife. Traditional roles include the wife's responsibility to bear and raise children, to be faithful, to serve the family, to loyally subordinate her interests to those of her husband, to adapt to subordination to her spouse and his family members, and to tolerate the limitations of her sphere of activity. In this case, the following are necessary from the husband's side to maintain the harmony of family relations: loyalty to the mother of his children, economic security and protection of the family, maintaining family authority and control, making major decisions in the family, and providing alimony in the event of a divorce. The husband's role requires giving his wife his feelings and a courageous attitude towards her, mutual love and tenderness, providing money for buying clothes, entertainment, maintaining social contacts, and spending free time with his wife.

CONCLUSION

The role of partners requires both the wife and the husband to contribute economically to the family in accordance with their income, share responsibility for children, participate in household chores, and share legal responsibilities. The husband

must also accept his wife's equal status and agree to her equal participation in making any decisions, and take equal responsibility for maintaining the family position. The factors that ensure stability in young families are diverse. Young spouses agree on the extent to which the wife will devote herself to professional activities in the family, to what extent she will fulfill family responsibilities, the consistency of the spouses' views on spending free time, the man's and the woman's leisure time outside the family, for example, with friends, the equal distribution of child-rearing and financial support responsibilities in the family, the consistency of interpersonal roles, and taking into account the specifics of each other's positions in marriage and in the family, are among them.

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